

The epistemology of human rights is cherished in Islamic law and its compatibility with international law.

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Abstract— Human beings are the super organism granted the gift of consciousness of life by the Almighty God and endowed with an intrinsic legal value to their humanity that shall be guarded and protected respecting dignity regardless of your cultural, religious, race, or physical background, you want to be treated equally for the reason for being human.

Islam graces the essential integrity of humanity and confirms the freedom and accountability impact on individuality and the open societal sphere including the moral, economic, and political aspects. Human Rights allows people to live with dignity, equality, justice, freedom, and peace. The Kantian approach to morality expresses that ethical actions follow universal moral laws. Hence, human rights are based upon the normative approaches setting international standards to promote, guard, and protect the fundamental rights of the people. Islam is a divine religion commanding human rights based upon the principles of social justice and regulates all facets of the moral and spiritual ethics of Muslims besides bringing balance abreast in the non-Muslims to respect their lives with safety and security and property. The Canon law manifests the faith and equality amongst Christianity regulating the communal dignity to build and promote the sanctity of Holy life (can. 208 to 223). This concept of the community is developed after the insight of the Islamic 'canon law' which is the code of revelation itself and inseparable from the natural part of the salvation of mankind.

The etymology and history of human rights is a polemical debate in a preview of Islamic and Western culture. On the other hand, international law is meticulous about the fundamental part of Canon law that focuses on the communal political, social, and economic relationship. The evolving process of human rights is an exclusive universal thought regarding an open society that forms a legal base for the constituent of international instruments of the protection of Human Rights viz. UDHR. On the other side, Muslim scholars emphasize that human rights are devolving around Islamic law. Both traditions need a dire explanation of contemporary openness for bringing the harmonious universal law acceptable and applicable to the international communities concerning the anthropology of political, economic, and social aspects of a human being.

Keywords— Human Rights-based approach (HRBA), Human Rights in Islam, Evolution of Universal Human Rights, Conflict in Western and Islamic Human Rights.

I. INTRODUCTION

THIS Sequencing human rights, Sequencing dignity, Sequence humanity. Human Rights have a causality relationship with the dignity of human-being that fleshes humanity to do part exclusively with their social class, race, gender, religion, skill, or any other possessive factor other than them being human. Human Rights are a social nucleus of

Humanity that disposes of generous behavior respecting mankind's inherent rights that should be protected and secured with its full solemnity of freedom, liberty, equity, and equality. Human Rights is a set stretch of human dignity that has the fundamental essentiality of a human being.

To understand the conceptual description of human rights and its relationship with the Islamic Jurisprudence and Universal implication, it is deemed to have a thoughtful assessment of the essentialization of human beings with social, political, and economic criteria realizing for human rights comparatively given in both documents of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the Cairo Declaration of Human rights in Islam. It will be careful to grasp considerate thoughts about the Law, Jurisprudence, and Islamic law earlier to dive into the comparative description.

Islamic Jurisprudence is inclusive and deliberates the divine code imparts the religious law regarding every facet and dimension of human life that are eternal and not amendable. These laws are balanced, convenient, and congruent with man's nature being formulated by the One who created organisms and knows the everlasting ends of living life. The Western and Islamic Scholars are eloquently constructing distinctive approaches to human rights involving the questions connecting to Islamic doctrine and that given in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

The foundation of human rights is based upon the principles of social justice providing equal rights and warning against despotic rule and practice by avoiding exploitation, corruption, and manipulation against mankind. Islamic jurisprudence provides propounded social justice provoking the discrimination of creed, language, color, and affluent one other.

Though human rights are an essential dynamic of open societies but cannot be guaranteed all the time in an unqualified way and set some limitations. Hence the sovereign state is in authority for both the protection and restriction of human rights. At the same time, the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) exercises a subsidiary role and applies the systematic external check on the state's regulation of human rights, and the victim can appraise the European Court of Human Rights and request compensation.

It is a bit controversial in the implementation of western designed Universal Human Rights that raise international debate over violations appearing in Muslim countries with

political motives to keep them under due pressure and stress while ignoring the Western countries from any accountability with a pretext to desecration. The constant conflict manifests the claim of the universality of declared human rights articulated by the United Nations and the universality ideology of human rights conferred through the Holy Quran and Sharia. Western considered the universalities of human rights overhead the Sheria and Muslim scholars considered the Islamic laws supreme, everlasting, and explicit till the day of judgment. Accordingly, Islamic and Western Scholars are constructing distinguishing approaches to argue the Human Rights involving Islamic mandate and that outlined in the International Bill of Human Rights.

The question raised is what creates the human right granted universal thoroughness, conspicuous contemporary vision, and approach, and also its afflicting religious and regional conflicts.

THESIS STATEMENT

The plain and instinctive purpose of this essay is to overview the research conducted on the genomics of Human Rights, parse the congruity, clashes, and misconception between the Islamic human right and Western-designed international human rights recognized with an assessment of contemporary thought of Human Right-Based Approach (HRBA) in the development of both doctrines.

PRIMARY SOURCE

This paper is designed to collect the data from SOAS's library, JSTOR, and MLA recitation machine. The primary source will be Laws, acts, and international covenants. The secondary source will focus on the academic literature described in books, and Journal articles relating to the topic. Writing, footnotes, and bibliography would be styled under the OSCOLA form.

METHODOLOGY

This paper will insight thematic approach for structuring a literature review of previous research work done on this sensitive area of study that is synthesizing the works for intuitive assessment of normativity impact spawned to understand the true Islamic ideology, compatibility with Western tradition, and its causality over societies of various community and countries.

Conceptual Investigation of the Human Rights

Human Rights are thought to be a moral right of a higher degree stemming from human needs which are socially constructed on moral and natural conceptions of human beings that conditions the necessity for a life of dignity. The United Nations has promisingly formulated the all-inclusive frame of the Universal and International Code of Human Rights inclusive of social, civil, cultural, political, and economic rights to which all countries can adhere and implement.

The basic principle of these human rights are protected in the Charter of the United Nations (1945) and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) which exclusively explained that "human rights are inherent fundamental rights of all human beings which are protected and can be exercised without any discrimination those includes the right to life and liberty, freedom from slavery and torture, freedom of opinion

and expression, the right to work and education, and many more".

Man, needs are evolutionary growing from substance to the dire need for protection, dignity, equality, and social justice to safeguard his disposition to the utmost of its materially and spiritually progressive meeting with contemporary ethics of scientific and technological demand. The deontology development of human rights is based upon the principles of social justice-based an action of righteousness delivering equal rights and desisting from unlawful action like despotic rule and practice by avoiding exploitation, corruption, and manipulation against mankind.

Human rights and freedom are considered to be the gift of God conferred an inalienable amount of dignity, honor, prestige, and security to mankind in conformity against indiscriminative law and authority while promoting and safeguarding society against crime and deviant behavior with an application of structural detrimental and retroactive action. Hence, Islam's commands of human rights provide a safe and effective foundation in respect of legal, social, and economic autonomy and guard, in contrast, to somewhat infringement of them.

The human being possesses a special intrinsic value to their humanity essentialization of respect as regards dignity, safety, equality, and justice regardless of who they are. Human dignity is attained by persuading the human rights that stresses universally in all religions like Judaism, Christianity, Buddhism, and prominently in Islam. Hence, the ideology of Human Rights emphasizes rationality and religious conscience to live a better social life. Man is gifted with an innate character of morality by God that inspires mankind to observe parity and fair dealing with others if not, he will miss the quality of humanity which is the outcome of moral consciousness.

An open society ensures democracy, rule of law, and human rights. The sovereign state provides guaranteed protection of human rights, and equal treatment to all people without culture, religion, physical, or racial background. The protection of human rights turned out to be the legal international instrument through an international covenant known as the European Convention of Human Rights (ECHR) where the people can get enforced the violation of their rights through the European Court of Human Rights.

Though human rights are an essential dynamic of open societies but cannot be guaranteed all the time in an unqualified way and set some limitations. Although personal security is important, police can issue a warrant for the search of the house to combat crime even without a search warrant, can check the person on different occasions. Hence, the sovereign state is entirely responsible for the protection of human rights but also obligated to restrict them. Maurice Cranston defined human rights as the substance of paramount importance and violation of these is tantamount to grave injury to social justice (Cranston 1967).

The U.S. Declaration of Independence (July 4, 1776) declared the principle of human events which mainly emphasized that people are bestowed with natural rights to life; freedom, and liberty that blessed the happiness by God who is

only the creator and supreme lawmaker and therefrom possesses the right to choose own government. Human Rights are abstract morality, social-economic, and political norms that emerged through legislative action of an enactment, custom, and legal stare decides at the national level, and through covenant in the international law and decision made by the ECtHR which urge to protect the society from distinctive discrimination and abuses.

The principles of human rights are mapped in many manuscripts of nations as well as these are intrinsically and comprehensively composed and laid down in the United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) besides the two international treaties; the International Covenant established on Civil and Political Rights 'ICCPR' (1966) and the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights 'ICESCR' (1966). The Universal Declaration contains the major six groups of human rights Security rights, Due process rights, Liberty rights, Political rights, Equality rights, and social rights. These were subsequently extended by including the seventh category as the Minority and Group rights. The Universal Declaration also counted in the Social Rights to cover the aspect of education, food, health services, and employment in the treaty of the 'Social Covenant of International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966) besides taking an opportunity for scientific progress and applications enforceable since 1976.

Civil and Political Human Rights are mainly established in the most important bills of rights including the English Bill of Rights of 1688, the US Declaration of Independence of 1776, The U.S. Bill of Rights (1789), the French Declaration of the Rights of Man and Citizen (1789) which become a part in French Constitution in 1791. Human rights are further developed in International Law with the present source of the Universal Declaration and treaties such as the European Convention, ICCPR (1966), ICESCR (1966), the American Convention on Human Rights, and the African Charter on Human and People's Rights. The United Nations is constantly focusing on all spheres of human rights for securing humanity from all tangible and intangible risks and dangers.

UN Human Rights and Climate Change organization is mandated to counter the environmental threat posing to the basic right to live a safe and standard life. The United Nations vigorously concentrated on the aspect of vulnerable people to safeguard their fundamental rights. For example, The International Convention on the elimination of all forms of racial discrimination (1965); the Convention on the elimination of all forms of discrimination against women (1979); the Convention on the Rights of the Children (1989); the Convention on the Rights of the person with disabilities (2007); the declaration on the Rights of indigenous peoples (2007) and the rights concerning to women and minorities.

Islam encourages the empathetic and a good deal with the people with whom one interacts regularly including neighbors. The Holy Prophet SAW said that "man is not a believer in God who eat and fills his stomach while his neighbor is hungry". Islam promotes social justice on basis of righteousness for equal delivery of possessions and opportunities without partiality of

religion, social class, race, and order to desist and end slavery. In the Quran, Allah SWT promises equal recompense to men and women if they acted on fair belief and virtuously act in good conduct. In the verse (16:97) Quran says that "whoever does righteousness, whether the male or female, whilst he is a believer in God then Allah will surely cause him to live a good life, and He will surely give them their reward [in the Hereafter] according to the best of what they used to do." [Noble Quran 16:97] The Holy Prophet, Muhammad SAW said: "Verily Allah SWT does not look to your faces and your wealth but He looks to your heart and your deeds".

The Jurisprudence of Islamic Human Rights Concerning Modern Approaches

Jurisprudence is the work and science of trying to define law. Islamic jurisprudence is developed by the four famous interpreters known as imam Maliki, Shafi, Hanafi, and Hanbali. Islamic jurisprudence is enlightened by the Islamic Jurists (Fiqh) during the ninth-tenth in light of Islamic human legal jurisprudence that embraces Sharia. Therefore, most of the part of Sharia contains the code of life, near about 8% is about the rules and regulations and nearly 2% comprises the Sharia law. Muslim women's attire particularly hijab is an Islamic tradition, not mandatory like praying and fasting.

The Human Rights mentioned in Islamic Jurisprudence are the natural product of divine commands about dignity and equality based upon the practices of faith, beliefs, deeds, and societal social behavior throughout the people irrespective of religious or regional discernment. Those are entirely stemmed from the principle of humanity, righteousness, and piety. This thought is eloquently illustrated in the final sermon by the Holy Prophet, Muhammad (PBUH), and professed the element of discrimination that "no Arab has any superiority over a non-Arab and non-Arab over Arab, nor does a white man have any superiority over a black man or vice versa, You are all the children of Adam, and Adam was created from clay." Verses (16:90) of the Holy Quran say: "God commands justice, doing good, and generosity with the ancestors, and He, Allah forbids the act what is shameful, blameworthy, and oppressive, He, Allah teaches you, so that you may take heed". The Holy Prophet, Muhammad SAW created the first Islamic Society in the holy city, Medina, by eliminating the social all-evil menace by developing the rule of law and justice, respecting humanity, religious and economic autonomy, social parity, life, and ownership security for all individual and to the society at the large.

It is a principal perception of human dignity that abridged human rights with various religious, cultural, and philosophical doctrines. Kelsay and Twiss concluded that "virtually there are elements in all religious tradition that promote peace, endurance, lenience, freedom, dignity, social justice and, for the equal conduct of a person.

Rawls contended that the liberal code of political justice is comprised of the normative theory that surpasses the doctrine of "modus vivendi" and claims a practical priority of the society that can be resolved the conflicting values and beliefs based on "overlapping consensus. The structure of every human individual is not solitary a corporeal object but possesses

spirituality, thus they are principally spiritual beings. The spiritual activities flourish the intrinsic worth of human beings which is considered to be the source of Stoic doctrine and Christian philosophy that fortitude morality, prudence, and social justice. The great philosopher Immanuel Kant thought that human being possesses a better place in the organism thus having an 'intrinsic worth i.e., dignity', which implies that human has a certain right to be respected and enforced incapacity of moral responsibility.

Human Rights are integrated with a set of standards and fewer of those tantamount to infringement warrant the legal consequences. Hence, this involves a legal framework to direct and protect the constitutional fundamental rights of the people. The United Nations Statistics Division is engaging with States besides the NHRICS and other social and political actors to ensure the implementation of UDHR through good governance without that sustainably enforcing human rights is not possible. It requires a structural mechanism to launch good governance reforms for the protection, transparency, and accountability of human rights in all spheres of human life with the full enthusiasm and capacity of the government.

People somehow pretend to be behind the 'Veil of ignorance' but mostly in vain as human behavior cognizant them of the rational decision of the rights to self-actualization and contentment. Philosopher John Rawls elegantly explained this notion as a bare minimum feasible knowledge for rational decision-making which does not cause harm to the life of other people.

Evolutionary Relationship of Western Human Rights and Islamic Human Rights:

The etymology of human rights is traced in the religious transition and most eloquently mentioned in the Islamic resources. The polemic discussion aggressively started about universal human rights with the assumption that this composed western originality has an inadequate and partial application.

Muslim scholars previewed western motifs differently with a limited scope of application predominantly prevailing in western and non-western cultures. Western societies have changed the norms of Human Rights suited to the lives of Western people. Edmund Bourke ironically made a historic criticism of the concept that "Universal Human Rights derives from western construct and western societies that are implemented into non-western." Pollis and Schwab have clarified that the human rights philosophy is historically developed in Western Europe and North America, hence restrictedly linked to Occidental traditions. Bassam Tibi stated that Western human rights are a spinoff of European colonialism resulting in the dissemination of occidental cultural heritage.

Muslim Scholars, Abul A'la Mawdudi discorded the essentialist approach of human rights alluding to the Western aptitude for accrediting it in their account rather these are God gifted revealed in Holy Qur'an and clarified through the Hadith of the Holy Prophet Muhammad (PBUH). Mawdudi criticized the Universal Declaration of Human Rights as unfairly associated with Western ideology. He emphasizes this on the Islamic motif of human rights principally engrained in the

Quran and Sunnah (tradition) of the Holy Prophet Muhammad (PBUH). The philosophy of western human rights is the outcome aftermath of the French revolution. In 1789 the French recognized the fundamentals of Human Rights which recommends that society has the power to claim their rights. Similarly, colonialization penetrated the impact of the western culture in the native non-western culture.

Western human rights are mostly developed from the major occasions at the time that can be categorized into three-generation: The first generation of human rights are created in the eighteenth century through the American revolution in 1776 and the French revolution in 1789 that aims to secure the civil and political rights of people and stopping the government to infringes the liberty rights of the individual.

These human rights are recognized in the International Bill of Human Rights with the specification of the rights to individual freedom of speech, expression, and the right to own property. The second generation of human rights is grown in the nineteenth century on the eve of political and economic agitation made by the working class for securing their social, economic, and cultural rights. Thus, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights identifies the principle of rights based on first- and second-generation human rights. The socio-economic and political chaos of the people that emerged after the second world war is considered the root cause of the third generation of Human Rights that assumed the right of self-determination, environment, culture, and rights to development which were adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 1986.

Comparative Study of Two Declarations

Islam concentrates on the observance of good manners in the entire sphere of life. Allah (SWT) in Holy Quran says: "And indeed, you are of a great moral character" (68:4). "And those who abuse believing men and women, when they have not merited it, bear the weight of slander and clear wrongdoing" (Ahzaab33:58). Prophet Muhammad (SAW) said, "The most beloved of Allah's servants are those who having with the best manner" (Al-Bukhari). The cutting-edge argument between Western and Islamic Scholars is the subject of the compatibility of human rights in two legal traditions of Islamic Law with International Law. Western scholarship detests the Islamic ethos and unfairly criticizes human rights in the Islamic States, particularly on the issue of women's rights, children's rights, freedom of expression, and religious discourse. Whereas, Islamic scholarship believes the rights are eternally bestowed by God, the 'Creator of mankind' strictly in line with the description perceived in Holy Book and guided through Sharia. If we give a glance review at the philosophies advocated by the Muslim and Western philosophers, we will experience the coincidence of their different expressions on human rights. Muslim scholars believed that human rights do not base on thoughts but are in-built into mankind on natural justice. The appraisal of the principles outlined in both the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) and the Cairo Declaration of Human Rights in Islam (August 5, 1990) relatively furnish the learning to know the similarities and differences between them concerning diverse aspects of the human-being emerging the fundamental human rights.

Similarities between Islamic and International Human Rights

Apart from the discussion of dissimilarities prevailing between Islamic and international human rights due to variants factors, there exists a close vision and agreement on the fundamental rights concerning life, freedom, and justice.

Both the declarations encompass basic human rights in their manuscript of given principles: all human beings are born free and hold equal rights, with no discrimination, no slavery, possess the right to life, equal before and use of the law, no unfair detainment, no torture, and inhuman treatment, rights for the fair trial, innocent till proved guilty, right of privacy, right to marry and have a family, right to own things, right to speech and opinion, right to freedom and expression, right to education, right to hygienic and standard living, right of women to enjoy the protection of government and the society, right to movement and seeking legal asylum.

Right to participate in governmental functionaries, and finally but not least that these declarations stress that every human person is under obligation to strive for the promotion and protection of these rights and freedom so others cannot take benefit of them for his interest.

Differences between Islamic and International Human Rights

That the Islamic declaration makes concentration on the dignity possessed because of a human being and the acquired dignity attained by his righteousness and spiritual instinct, but UDHR missed this very chief conception. Islamic declaration emphasizes the divine attribution of Islam being a universal religion and derives knowledge, power, and life as a gift of God and, people are the servant and are equal to Him except those who are spiritually virtuous and upright. Consequently, the lawful imperativeness of human rights becomes sacred to be respected and saved. The universal declaration did correlate this conceptual relation.

Islamic declaration focus on the fame of man and human dignity should be protected after death towards his dead body and grave but the universal declaration in Article 3 attended to this point differently. Both the declaration recognizes the family as a basic unit and men and women have the right to build a family but within certain parameters and limitations. Islamic declaration assumed that marriage is the virtual source of family in the purview of the religion, but the universal declaration viewed this point differently and regards equal rights for men and women ignoring the religious embargo and focusing on alimony and divorce whereas the Islamic declaration eloquently explained that women have various positive rights is proportionate to her duties and obligations.

However, women have financial independence and their substance and means of living are made the onus of their husbands. The Islamic declaration places the social obligation of the government to pave the way and remove unlawful hurdles of marriage whereas, there is no such directive in the universal declaration. The Islamic declaration recognizes the social rights of neighbors, relatives, and parents but these are not considered in the universal declaration. The Islamic declaration described education as an integral part of human life

whereas, the universal declaration emphasized free education but was not obligatory. The Islamic declaration Article 10 stresses the right to follow innate religion which forbids exploitation whereas, the universal declaration permits the freedom of religion and opinion which is a controversial issue and a basis of the conflict between two ideologies.

The Islamic declaration vide article 11 asserted that man is born free hence, acquired the right to freedom and the right to be free from exploitation, slavery, and oppression. This tends to the servitude only and only to Almighty God. whereas, the Universal declaration solely rejects the slavery and servitude of other people. The Principle of the Islamic Declaration stresses lawful income and possession besides prohibiting usury, torturous, and cruelty to others.

It is confidently affirmed that there is no match of human rights proclaimed under the various covenant of the United Nations with Islamic human rights. The former is declaratory that objectively encourages protecting the rights of human-being while later scoping all living life and carrying a mandatory sanction by God. Europe, however, is biased to defend western values and tends to please the powering countries by ignoring the unlawful violation, particularly in Islamic countries like Palestine, Egypt, Iraq, Afghanistan, and occupied Kashmir.

II. CONCLUSION

Human Rights are an essential dynamic for upkeep and maintaining the dignity of mankind. These entirely stemmed from the principle of humanity, righteousness, and piety. Human Rights emphasize rationality and religious conscience to live a better indiscriminative social life. The concept of human rights is not novel in Islamic ideology. These are endowed in Holy Qur'an revealed by the Holy Prophet, Muhammad (PBUH).

Hence, human rights come under the extensive discourse of morality in the religious traditional framework where compliance is mandatory, and desecration is punishable. Modern human rights are distinctively created on two western declarations: the French and United States declarations. Eventually, the European Convention of Human Rights and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights have idiosyncratically formed the open society in western culture.

Human rights are considered a concrete legal tool as well as a moral idea in the hands of people in open societies as divergent to authoritarian systems. These are mostly absolutely absolute and non-derogated. However, occasionally under specific conditions attracts some legal limitations. The Muslim scholar of classical thought believes that contemporary norms of human rights are not compatible with Islamic tradition whilst scholars of liberal ideology placed more room in deliberation and explanation of Islamic code considering the Islamic law as supple to evolve new thought of openness of human rights congruent to the communities of Islamic tradition.

The Islamic Council established the Universal Islamic declaration of human rights in 1991 to deliberate and explain the Islamic ideology that may be comparatively congruent with Universal Human Rights and in addition compatible with these as provided in ICCPR. Nonetheless, could not resolve the

international contemporary disputed issue affecting gender viz. the rights of women affecting the various sphere of life as well as the quantum of punishment on the commit of various crimes in Islamic closed society.

These main issues led to criticism and havoc campaigns of anti-Muslimism that is to say 'islamophobia' in Britain. The Islamic scholar contended that the commands of God revealed in Qur'an cannot be amended and warrant compulsory compliance, instead of the Western approach to modern human rights that is liberal for the open society.

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